

ENHANCING LECTURER PERFORMANCE THROUGH THE ORGANIZATIONAL FACTORS, TALENT MANAGEMENT, AND ACHIEVEMENT MOTIVATION: A CASE STUDY OF LLDIKTI VI CENTRAL JAVA

SUNARSO ¹, IDA AJU BRAHMASARI ² and RIYADI NUGROHO ³

^{1,2,3} Docrotare Program, Univeristas 17 Agustus 1945 Surabaya.

Email: ¹sunarso66@gmail.com, ²brahmasari@untag-sby.ac.id, ³riyadi@untag-sby.ac.id

Abstract

The main issue of this study is that lecturers' performance, especially in research and community service, falls short, affecting lecturers' performance. This study analyzed the Influence of competence, perception of organizational support, self-efficacy, transformational leadership, talent management, and achievement motivation on lecturer performance registered in LLDIKTI VI of Central Java. This quantitative study surveyed faculty members from private universities in LLDIKTI VI Central Java, analyzing their responses with descriptive statistics and Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) using AMOS. The research aimed to test 14 hypotheses with a sample size of 342 faculty members. Based on the results of the study, it can be concluded that competency, perception of organizational support, self-efficacy, and transformational leadership have a significant effect on lecturers' talent management and achievement motivation. However, only competency and talent management have a significant impact on lecturer performance. Additionally, achievement motivation also has a significant effect on lecturer performance. Therefore, improving these factors could lead to better performance outcomes in the academic setting.

Keywords: Competence, Perception of Organizational Support, Self-Efficacy, Transformational Leadership, Talent Management, Achievement Motivation, Performance.

PENDAHULUAN

Globalization has had significant impacts on higher education institutions in Indonesia, offering ample opportunities for universities to provide knowledge and technology services to the government, society, and the business world. The role and function of Indonesian universities as institutions implementing education and teaching, research, and community service are referred to as the *tridharma* (the three pillars) of higher education. As educational and teaching institutions, universities prepare educated graduates with academic and professional skills.

As research institutions, they engage in various research activities to scientifically address problems related to a field of science and technology and contribute to development. As institutions serving the community, universities undertake various activities to motivate, participate in, and support community development through the practical application of knowledge and technology. Private universities play a strategic role within the national education system of Indonesia, aligning with historical, philosophical, national, and scientific and technological development demands.

Their current roles and functions are increasingly complex and competitive at various levels (local, regional, and international), in line with societal expectations. Therefore, universities must pay attention to all human resources that support the success of their organization. Lecturers have a very important role in carrying out the *tridharma* of higher education. They are not only teachers, but also curriculum builders, controllers of academic regulations, creating a conducive learning environment, and influencing the intellectual and social environment of the campus. Lecturers have the responsibility to educate students to become individuals who have the skills needed in their lives and careers, while paying attention to moral attitudes. Lecturers' duties and responsibilities also include research and community service, as well as contributing to the delivery of information and updates in higher education. Apart from that, they have a moral responsibility to practice and pass on the values of Pancasila to students. Therefore, they need to receive serious attention so that they can carry out their functions optimally and improve their performance for the smooth functioning of higher education.

The evaluation of lecturers' performance serves as a crucial benchmark for enhancing the quality of teaching, fostering lecturer self-improvement, boosting student satisfaction with teaching, elevating lecturer job satisfaction, achieving university program goals, and enhancing public perception of higher education institutions. The current situation in the field, as a preliminary study of lecturer performance, differs from what should ideally exist. Deviations in lecturer performance are prevalent in universities, particularly private ones. One of the issues is the lack of readiness among lecturers in mastering teaching materials, resulting in students not gaining sufficient depth of knowledge. Another emerging problem is the minimal research output due to the time devoted to teaching hours. Additionally, many lecturers are drawn to positions in various government agencies or educational institutions, further complicating matters. This issue deserves special attention to further advance the affiliated higher education institution. With such disparities in mind, researchers aim to delve deeper into lecturer performance.

Lecturer performance is a critical factor in ensuring the quality management of universities, as it serves as a gauge of personnel's capabilities and competencies in fulfilling their duties and responsibilities. According to Hasibuan (2014:45), work performance or performance achievement is the outcome of someone's work based on dedication and time. Etymologically, performance in English is referred to as "performance," or it can also be called work achievement or work implementation. In order to enhance lecturer performance, the process involves collecting information and knowledge about lecturer workload (BKD), which is a representation of lecturers' activities in education, research, and community service, as well as supporting factors. BKD is assessed based on Semester Credit Units (SKS) according to the Directorate General of Higher Education standards (Hamukti et al., 2017:32). Dosen's teaching performance generally demonstrates high performance; however, research and community service aspects are still suboptimal. Yet, lecturer performance measurements are not only based on their teaching but also on their research and community service endeavors. This condition also applies to lecturers within the Higher Education Service Institutions (LLDIKTI) VI Jawa Tengah. The low interest among lecturers in conducting research can be observed from the low number of lecturers receiving research grants from LLDIKTI.

Further research is necessary to identify specific talent management strategies that contribute to improving the performance of lecturers at LLDIKTI VI Central Java. Additionally, it is important to gain a deeper understanding of the factors that influence lecturers' motivation to achieve in the academic environment. This research gap includes an exploration of how work environment, job characteristics, and personal factors affect lecturers' motivation to achieve. Such research can provide guidance for developing interventions or programs that can improve the performance of lecturers at LLDIKTI VI Central Java by boosting their motivation to achieve.

THEORETICAL STUDY

In order to manage human resources strategically, Becker established Human Capital Management (HCM) in 1964. Employee development would aid in the accomplishment of corporate objectives since they were valuable resources that might improve performance inside the company. The effectiveness of HCM is also influenced by elements including leadership, organizational structure, work environment, and HR procedures. Human capital management theory encompasses four fundamental components: Recruitment and Selection, which involves the process of acquiring and selecting individuals that meet the organization's specific needs and culture; Training and Development, which facilitates employee skill and knowledge development to increase productivity and flexibility; Compensation and Benefits, which create fair and competitive compensation systems that inspire, retain, and attract personnel; and Performance Evaluation and Management, which measures performance, provides feedback, and promotes career development to ensure employees perform at high levels and align with business objectives.

Competence

Competency refers to a person's ability to perform effectively in a particular job or situation based on the required skills, knowledge, and work attitudes. Different experts have defined it in various ways. According to the Training Agency in Sudarmanto (2009), competence is the ability to carry out activities by expected work standards. Wirawan (2009) describes competence as a combination of knowledge, skills, behavior, and experience needed to perform work effectively. Mitrani et al. (1992) and Spencer & Spencer (1993) define competency in terms of individual characteristics that contribute to work effectiveness. Mathis & Jackson (2001) also link competence to individual or team performance achievements. Lecturer competency indicators, such as quality reflection, work exploration, and career control, have been identified by Akkermans et al. (2013).

Jeffrey & Febrianti (2019), Damanik et al. (2019), and Nawangsari & Sutawidjaya (2019) all found that competency effects talent management. According on the literature review and past research, the following hypothesis is proposed:

Hypothesis 1: Competence has a significant effect on talent management among LLDIKTI VI Central Java lecturers.

Damanik et al. (2019), Nawangsari & Sutawidjaya (2019), and Suardika (2019) all found that competence influences motivation. According on the literature review and past research, the following hypothesis is proposed:

Hypothesis 2: Competence significantly influences the accomplishment motivation of LLDIKTI VI Central Java instructors.

Research conducted by Hairuddin et al (2017), Budiansyah et al. (2020), Jeffrey & Febrianti (2019), and Nawangsari & Sutawidjaya (2019) concluded that competence influences motivation. Based on the literature review and previous research, the following hypothesis is proposed:

Hypothesis 3: Competence has a significant effect on the performance of LLDIKTI VI Central Java lecturers.

Perception of Organizational Support

Perceived organizational support refers to the opinion that employees have about how much their organization values their contributions and cares about their well-being. According to Benlioglu (2014), positive working conditions and effective HR procedures can help create favorable impressions among employees. However, Luthans (2005) argues that perception is a personal interpretation of a situation and does not always reflect reality. Many studies have shown that there is a positive correlation between perceived organizational support and organizational citizenship behavior (Hutchison, 1997). In addition, Eisenberger et al. (2002) and Wang et al. (2020) suggest that moral support, trust, and care are three indicators of perceived organizational support.

Research conducted by Isa & Ibrahim (2020) concluded that organizational support influences talent management. Based on the literature review and previous research, the following hypothesis is proposed:

Hypothesis 4: Organizational support has a significant effect on talent management of LLDIKTI VI Central Java lecturers.

Research conducted by Siddiqua & Patrick (2018) and Ompok & Teo (2021) concluded that perceptions of organizational support influence motivation. Based on the literature review and previous research, the following hypothesis is proposed:

Hypothesis 5: Perception of organizational support has a significant effect on the achievement motivation of LLDIKTI VI Central Java lecturers.

Research conducted by Dewiana (2020), Nelwan et al. (2019), and Isa & Ibrahim (2020) concluded that perceptions of organizational support influence performance. Based on the literature review and previous research, the following hypothesis is proposed:

Hypothesis 6: Perception of organizational support has a significant effect on the performance of LLDIKTI VI Central Java lecturers.

Self-Efficacy

Self-efficacy is the belief in one's ability to take action, achieve goals, and overcome challenges. For teachers, self-efficacy is shaped by their perception of internal factors influenced by their social environment. If teachers have confidence in their abilities, they will improve their teaching practices. Boosting self-efficacy is crucial for every teacher to reach their full potential. The greater their belief in their abilities, the easier it will be to enhance their quality and performance. Schwarzer et al. (1995) suggest that the level of task demands, one's ability to complete the task, and one's confidence in finishing the task are indicators of self-efficacy.

Research conducted by Damanik et al. (2019) concluded that self-efficacy influences talent management. Based on the literature review and previous research, the following hypothesis is proposed:

Hypothesis 7: Self efficacy has a significant effect on talent management of LLDIKTI VI Central Java lecturers

Research conducted by Damanik et al. (2019), Maraghi et al (2018), and Silalahi & Silvianita (2021), concluded that self-efficacy influences motivation. Based on the literature review and previous research, the following hypothesis is proposed:

Hypothesis 8: Self efficacy has a significant effect on achievement motivation at LLDIKTI VI Central Java.

Research conducted by Muharlisiani et al (2021), and Batubara (2021) concluded that self-efficacy influences performance. Based on the literature review and previous research, the following hypothesis is proposed:

Hypothesis 9: Self-efficacy has a significant effect on the performance of LLDIKTI VI Central Java lecturers.

Transformational Leadership

Transformational leadership is defined by Robbin & Judge (2018) as a type of leadership that inspires and motivates people to take extraordinary action. These leaders are able to instill trust, admiration, and loyalty in their followers, encouraging them to go beyond their usual expectations. According to Kharis (2015), transformational leaders have a remarkable impact on their followers, convincing them to put aside their personal interests and believe in their ability to create a better future. Edison et al. (2016) note that transformational leaders are able to create significant transformations within themselves and their organizations. Ultimately, transformational leadership can influence how followers perceive challenges, motivating them to work harder to achieve organizational goals. Grošelj et al. (2020) identified five indicators of a transformational leadership style: idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, individualized consideration, and contingent reward.

Harun et al. (2020) and Sadeli (2021) found that transformative leadership influences talent management. According on the literature review and past research, the following hypothesis is proposed:

Hypothesis 10: Transformational leadership has a significant effect on talent management among LLDIKTI VI Central Java instructors.

Research conducted by Jiang & Chen (2018) and Suardika (2019) concluded that transformational leadership influences motivation. Based on the literature review and previous research, the following hypothesis is proposed:

Hypothesis 11: Transformational leadership has a significant effect on achievement motivation at LLDIKTI VI Central Java.

Research conducted by Muharlisiani et al (2021), Sani & Maharani (2012), Mulyadi (2017), and Suardika (2019) concluded that transformational leadership influences performance. Based on the literature review and previous research, the following hypothesis is proposed:

Hypothesis 12: Transformational leadership has a significant effect on the performance of LLDIKTI VI Central Java lecturers.

Talent Management

Talent management is a crucial aspect of managing human resources within an organization. The process involves aligning the skills and talents of workers with the strategic goals of the company. As Febriani (2012) and Pella & Afifah (2011) noted, talent management includes recruiting, attracting, developing, and retaining talent. The goal is to hire employees who consistently deliver high performance. According to Davis & Cutt (2007), talent is a desirable attribute that can exist at all levels and roles. As Chambers et al. (1998) established, talent management is the process of developing human resources based on certain talents or skills. Key indicators of talent management include recruitment and selection, retention, training and development, and performance management, as highlighted by Taamneh et al. (2021).

Research conducted by Selvanathan et al (2019), Nelwan et al. (2019), Isa & Ibrahim (2020), Nawangsari & Sutawidjaya (2019), and Sopiah et al (2021) concluded that talent management influences performance. Based on the literature review and previous research, the following hypothesis is proposed:

Hypothesis 13: Talent management has a significant effect on the performance of LLDIKTI VI Central Java lecturers.

Achievement Motivation

Achievement motivation, as outlined by McClelland (1997), encompasses the desire to excel, surpassing others in various contexts, emphasizing three fundamental needs: achievement, affiliation, and power. This concept aligns with research by Karagiannis et al. (2011), which categorizes motivation into intrinsic and extrinsic forms. Intrinsic motivation involves a sense of engagement in work, supportive leadership, job attractiveness, career advancement, and recognition for good performance, while extrinsic motivation includes factors like job security,

salary, discipline, working conditions, and mutual respect. Indicators of achievement motivation include the effort put into work and performance outcomes, contingent upon the employee's skill level and their perception of how effort translates into performance, influenced by past experiences (Mangkunegara, 2012:77). Further studies by Fernet et al. (2008) and Panisoara et al. (2020) highlight intrinsic motivation and identified regulations as key indicators of work motivation.

Research conducted by Muharlisiani et al (2021), Hairuddin et al (2017), Bangun et al (2018), Budiansyah et al. (2020), Nawangsari & Sutawidjaya (2019), Mulyadi (2017), Sarippudin & Handayani (2017) Srikaningsih & Setyadi (2015), and Heriyanto et al. (2018) concluded that motivation affects performance. Based on the literature review and previous research, the following hypothesis is proposed:

Hypothesis 14: Achievement motivation has a significant effect on the performance of LLDIKTI VI Central Java lecturers.

Lecturer Performance

In assessing the performance of higher education institutions, the role of a lecturer can be divided into several functions, including as an educator, researcher, community service provider, mentor, leader, innovator, and motivator. As an educator, a lecturer is expected to have good teaching achievements, guide students, and produce teaching materials. As a researcher, a lecturer is expected to be able to design and conduct research programs, as well as produce scientific publications. As a community service provider, a lecturer is expected to be involved in service activities, including designing proposals and implementing service programs. As a leader, a lecturer is expected to have a strong personality, understand the conditions of fellow lecturers and students, and be able to make decisions and communicate effectively. As an innovator, a lecturer is expected to be able to create new ideas and implement innovations in study programs. Lastly, as a motivator, a lecturer is expected to be able to create a conducive work environment and apply the principles of reward and punishment. According to Larasati & Prajogo (2022), the performance evaluation of lecturers can be seen from the indicators of In Role Performance and Research and Scientific Publication Activities.

RESEARCH METHOD

The present study is a quantitative research employing survey method and descriptive research type. The research was conducted in private universities under the purview of LLDIKTI VI Central Java, spanning from August to December 2022. The data utilized in the study was quantitative in nature, obtained through a questionnaire distributed among the faculty members of private universities under LLDIKTI VI Central Java. The study population was comprised of 68 faculty members from private universities under LLDIKTI VI Central Java, who had been accredited with a ranking of C or higher among a total of 2,367 faculty members. The sample size was determined to be 342 faculty members using the Slovin's formula. The survey questionnaire utilized a 5-point Likert scale. Descriptive data analysis techniques were employed, which included the characteristics of the respondents and the quantitative responses

of the respondents, using statistical frequency method and frequency distribution tables. Additionally, the study also utilized quantitative analysis through Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) technique utilizing AMOS.

After the consideration of 14 hypotheses, a comprehensive research conceptual framework was developed.

Figure 1: Research Conceptual Framework

In this research, seven variables will be studied. The seven variables are classified into three parts, namely independent variables (X), intervening variables (Z), and dependent variables (Y). These three variable classifications can be explained as follows:

1. Exogenous variables are competence (X1), perception of organizational support (X2), self-efficacy (X3), and transformational leadership (X4).
2. The endogenous variable is lecturer performance (Y).
3. Intervening variables are talent management (Z1), and achievement motivation (Z2).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Description of Respondent Characteristics

The research indicates that a majority of the lecturers in the sample were women with permanent employment status and have a second-degree (Master's degree) education. Most of them hold functional positions as Assistant Experts and rank III B. It was also found that a

majority of them have not been certified, suggesting that certification has not been a primary focus in private universities with C accreditation. The majority of lecturers fall in the age group of 31-40 years and have 2-5 years of service, indicating that they are relatively young and new to work experience. Based on these characteristics, it can be inferred that although the lecturers have the necessary educational qualifications, most of them are still at the initial level of functional positions and ranks, and have not been certified.

Table 1: Respondent Characteristics

Profil responden	Uraian	Frekuensi	Persentase
Sex	Male	73	21,3
	Female	269	78,7
	Total	342	100,0
Employment status	Assigned to a Private University	2	0,6
	Special Lecturer	5	1,5
	Permanent lecturer	335	98,0
	Total	342	100,0
Educational	Undergraduate	5	1,5
	Master	335	98,0
	Doctor	2	0,6
	Total	342	100,0
Functional	n.d	32	9,4
	Expert Assistant	185	54,1
	Lector	125	36,5
	Total	342	100,0
Rank	n.d	33	9,6
	III A	1	0,3
	III B	183	53,5
	III C	120	35,1
	III D	5	1,5
	Total	342	100,0
Certification	Not Certified	217	63,5
	Certified	125	36,5
	Total	342	100,0
Age	21-30	33	9,6
	31-40	187	54,7
	41-50	110	32,2
	51-60	7	2,0
	61-70	5	1,5
	Total	342	100,0
Years of service	2-5 years	162	47,4
	6-10 years	117	34,2
	11-15 tahun	55	16,1
	More than 15 years	8	2,3
	Total	342	100,0

Description of Questionnaire Answers

➤ *Competence*

Lecturers who work at private universities with good accreditation in LLDIKTI VI Central Java are perceived to have high competence, especially when it comes to reflecting on quality. However, the lowest indicator of perceived competence is work exploration. Most of these lecturers have a second-degree (Master's degree) education and permanent employment status, as well as functional positions as Expert Assistants, which can support a high level of agreement on competence. Despite their relatively young age and limited work experience, the high level of agreement indicates good progress in their professional development. However, most lecturers have not been certified, which can affect their work exploration, especially in keeping up with the latest information developments. Efforts are needed to improve the qualifications and certification of these lecturers as a step towards supporting the development of their talents and careers.

➤ *Perception of Organizational Support*

Lecturers who work at private universities with good accreditation at LLDIKTI VI Central Java feel that they receive high levels of support from the organization, especially when it comes to attention. Most of the respondents are permanent employees and hold functional positions as Expert Assistants, which could contribute to their positive perceptions of organizational support. Although some respondents are not yet certified, they hope to receive more assistance from the organization, particularly with respect to the certification process. However, there are still some areas that need improvement, such as the organization's willingness to help lecturers deal with difficult situations and provide flexibility in working hours. To enhance support, universities can implement policies that provide work flexibility, conduct time management training, and offer mental well-being support programs for lecturers. By undertaking these measures, it is hoped that support for lecturers can be improved, creating a more inclusive and supportive work environment for all members of the academic community.

➤ *Self-Efficacy*

Lecturers working at private universities with good accreditation in LLDIKTI VI Central Java display a high level of self-efficacy. They are particularly confident in their ability to complete assignments and tackle challenges. The majority of respondents, especially those who have a permanent employment status and functional positions as Expert Assistants, feel assured that they can overcome problems with sufficient effort. However, there are still areas where improvement is needed, such as a lack of calm in facing difficulties and a lack of confidence in finding solutions. Universities can provide support through Mentoring and Coaching programs, as well as strengthening social support networks between lecturers. By taking these steps, it is hoped that the university can help lecturers strengthen their self-efficacy in dealing with various situations and improve their overall well-being.

➤ ***Transformational Leadership***

Lecturers at well-accredited private universities in LLDIKTI VI Central Java gave a positive assessment of transformational leadership, especially in inspirational motivation and exception management, with a very high average score. Even though the Intellectual Stimulation and Contingent Reward aspects are rated high, they are still in the high category on the transformational leadership perception indicator. Although most lecturers are relatively young and have limited work experience, the high level of agreement indicates their appreciation for this leadership style, especially in the context of motivation and effective management. Lecturers' level of education also influences their perception of leadership, with a greater appreciation of aspects such as inspirational motivation and effective management.

➤ ***Talent Management***

Private university lecturers with good accreditation at LLDIKTI VI Central Java perceive talent management at universities positively, particularly regarding recruitment, selection, and performance management, evidenced by a high level of agreement. However, retention training and development aspects are identified for improvement. The majority of respondents, influenced by higher education, expect clear policies and procedures related to talent management. Permanent employment status and functional positions lead to expectations of continued career support. To address retention training and development issues, universities can implement employee retention programs, enhance training opportunities, and encourage involvement in joint research projects. Additionally, stimulating intellectual environments and structured reward systems can further motivate lecturers to excel and contribute to overall academic productivity.

➤ ***Achievement Motivation***

The study reveals that the talent management indicators, particularly recruitment and selection, and performance management, are perceived with the highest level of agreement. However, retention, training, and development are considered to be aspects that need improvement. Respondents with higher education, permanent employment status, and functional positions as Expert Assistants influence their perception of talent management at universities. The study suggests that universities can develop employee retention programs, increase provision of continuous training and development programs, and encourage lecturers' involvement in joint research projects to address the aspects that still need improvement. To overcome intellectual stimulation and contingent rewards, universities can encourage innovation and career development by providing incentives or awards to lecturers who achieve certain creative and academic milestones. Additionally, designing structured reward systems can create a work culture that motivates and provides incentives for lecturers to continue to excel.

➤ ***Lecturer Performance***

Lecturers working at well-accredited private universities in LLDIKTI VI Central Java have been evaluated positively for their performance in terms of productivity, responsibility, and ability to carry out educational, teaching, and community service tasks. However, there is room

for improvement in scientific research and publications, particularly in relation to publications in international journals. Most of the respondents who hold permanent employment status and functional positions as Expert Assistants have been found to be performing well in completing academic tasks. The university can provide support to enhance the research infrastructure, offer research methodology training, provide incentives for publishing in international journals, and allocate resources for research to improve the overall reputation and academic contribution of the university.

Hypotesis Testing

Figure 2: Structural Model Estimation Results

Table 2: Testing of Direct Influence Structural Relationships

Hip.	Pengaruh Langsung			Std. Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Decision
H ₁	X1	→	Z1	0,052	0,064	0,914	0,361 ^{n.s.}	Rejected
H ₂	X1	→	Z2	0,342	0,060	6,310	0,000 [*]	Accepted
H ₃	X1	→	Y	0,164	0,051	2,939	0,003 [*]	Accepted
H ₄	X2	→	Z1	0,360	0,059	5,896	0,000 [*]	Accepted
H ₅	X2	→	Z2	0,205	0,051	3,817	0,000 [*]	Accepted
H ₆	X2	→	Y	0,034	0,044	0,586	0,558 ^{n.s.}	Rejected
H ₇	X3	→	Z1	0,053	0,055	0,969	0,332 ^{n.s.}	Rejected
H ₈	X3	→	Z2	0,301	0,050	5,882	0,000 [*]	Accepted
H ₉	X3	→	Y	0,240	0,043	4,494	0,000 [*]	Accepted
H ₁₀	X4	→	Z1	0,335	0,070	5,408	0,000 [*]	Accepted
H ₁₁	X4	→	Z2	0,260	0,061	4,656	0,000 [*]	Accepted
H ₁₂	X4	→	Y	0,054	0,054	0,909	0,363 ^{n.s.}	Rejected
H ₁₃	Z1	→	Y	0,337	0,049	5,440	0,000 [*]	Accepted
H ₁₄	Z2	→	Y	0,303	0,063	3,964	0,000 [*]	Accepted
X1 : Competency				Z1 : Talent Management				
X2 : Perception of Organizational Support				Z2 : Achievement Motivation				
X3 : Self Efficacy				Y : Lecturer Performance				
X4 : Transformasional Leadership								
* . Significant at the 0,05 level				n.s. not significant				

➤ **Competency has no significant effect on lecturers' Talent Management**

The results of coefficient estimation for the impact of competence on talent management show that the influence is insignificant. The CR value is 0.914, which is less than 1.96, and the p-value is 0.361, which is higher than the 5% real level. The resulting influence coefficient is only 0.052, indicating that the higher competence of lecturers in higher education does not necessarily have a strong impact on good talent management in that tertiary institution. The hypothesis testing results indicate that the level of lecturer competency does not significantly influence talent management in higher education. However, this does not mean that competency is not essential in the context of talent management. It suggests that other factors are more influential in the talent management process in the institution. This result contradicts research conducted by Jeffrey & Febrianti (2019), Damanik et al. (2019), and Nawangsari & Sutawidjaya (2019), who concluded that competence influences talent management.

➤ **Competency has a significant effect on lecturers' Achievement Motivation**

The findings of the coefficient estimation analysis reveal a significant influence of competence on achievement motivation, as indicated by a critical ratio (CR) value of 6.310, exceeding the conventional threshold of 1.96, and a p-value of 0.000, which is smaller than the 5% significance level. The estimated influence coefficient of 0.342 is positively oriented, suggesting that higher levels of lecturer competence correspond to greater achievement motivation. The obtained results of the hypothesis testing emphasize that lecturers who possess a higher degree of competence tend to exhibit higher levels of motivation to achieve academic excellence, owing to their enhanced confidence in their ability to perform academic tasks proficiently. Such an increased level of competence can bolster lecturers' teaching, research, and community service skills, leading to more effective and efficient goal attainment.

➤ ***Competency has a significant effect on lecturer Performance***

Based on the statistical analysis performed, it can be concluded that competence plays a significant role in the performance of lecturers. The p-value of 0.003, which is less than the commonly accepted significance level of 5%, indicates the presence of a statistically significant relationship between competence and lecturer performance. Additionally, the coefficient estimation value of 2.939, which exceeds the critical value of 1.96, further strengthens this conclusion.

The effect coefficient of 0.164 suggests a positive correlation between lecturer competence and student success. This finding implies that instructors who possess a high degree of competence are more capable of fulfilling their academic responsibilities, thereby enhancing their overall performance. It is worth noting that competence encompasses a range of attributes, including professionalism, work ethics, integrity, and profession-related obligations.

Lecturers who display a high level of professionalism, for instance, are more likely to engender trust among their students, colleagues, and other stakeholders. This trust, in turn, can translate into improved performance. Therefore, the results of this study underscore the importance of cultivating and maintaining a high level of competence among lecturers.

➤ ***Perception of Organizational Support has a significant effect on lecturer Talent Management***

The results of the coefficient estimation indicate that perceived organizational support has a significant impact on talent management. The CR value of 5.896 is greater than 1.96, and the p-value of 0.000 is smaller than the 5% real level. The resulting influence coefficient of 0.360 is positive, suggesting that higher perceived support from the university indicates higher talent management.

Perceived organizational support refers to the belief of lecturers that the university values their contributions and provides the necessary resources to achieve success. The study suggests that when universities offer adequate support, such as recognition, facilities, or talent development opportunities, it increases the effectiveness of talent management.

The perception of positive organizational support greatly influences the talent management of lecturers at private universities with good LLDIKTI VI accreditation in Central Java.

➤ ***Perception of Organizational Support has a significant effect on lecturers' Achievement Motivation***

The present study examined the coefficient estimation results of the influence of perceived organizational support on achievement motivation, which revealed a significant influence with a CR value of 3.817 (greater than 1.96) and a significance value (p-value) of 0.000 (smaller than the 5% real level). The resulting influence coefficient of 0.205 (positive) indicated that the higher the level of perceived support provided by the university to the lecturer, the higher their achievement motivation would be. These findings suggest that when lecturers feel supported by their institutions, both in terms of recognition for their performance and adequate facilities, they tend to be more motivated to achieve their targets, such as improving the quality of

teaching, research, or community service. The results of this study are consistent with prior research, which has demonstrated that the better the perception of organizational support provided to employees, the greater the employees' achievement motivation increases. Specifically, the present findings corroborate the conclusions of Siddiqua & Patrick (2018) and Ompok & Teo (2021), which also reported that perceptions of organizational support have a positive influence on motivation. Overall, these results have important implications for institutions seeking to improve employee motivation and performance.

➤ ***Perception of Organizational Support has no significant effect on lecturer Performance***

With a significance value (p-value) of 0.558 (above the 5% significance level) and a coefficient estimation value of 0.586 (less than 1.96), the impact of perceived organizational support on lecturer performance is not statistically significant. With a coefficient of influence of only 0.034, which is almost zero, the greater the perceived support from the university among lecturers does not appear to have a significant effect on raising lecturer performance. Individuals make contributions that are perceived as organizational support, and the organization subsequently pays attention to and cares for their well-being. This idea states that people believe the organization will provide appropriate attention and welfare following their performance contribution (Eisenberger et al., 1986).

Nonetheless, the results of this study showed that lecturer performance was not significantly impacted by the notion of organizational support. The alternate premise that arose was that professors at universities with Good accreditations did not feel organizational support, hence lecturer performance could not improve in the sense that organizational support did not influence performance. A lecturer's motivation, level of expertise, experience, and expectations are among the human aspects that impact their success. Although perceived organizational support is vital, individual characteristics can have a significant impact on performance. If instructors lack motivation or competence, the perception of organizational support may be insufficient to dramatically improve their performance. This conclusion is inversely related to the research undertaken by Dewiana (2020), Nelwan et al., (2019), and Isa & Ibrahim (2020) who concluded that perceptions of organizational support influence performance.

➤ ***Self-Efficacy has no significant effect on lecturers' Talent Management***

The results of the coefficient estimation for the impact of self-efficacy on talent management indicate that the influence is not significant. The CR value is 0.969, which is less than 1.96, and the p-value is 0.332, which is greater than the 5% significance level. The resulting influence coefficient is only 0.053, which is close to zero. In simpler terms, these results suggest that the higher self-efficacy of lecturers in higher education does not necessarily have a strong impact on good talent management in that tertiary institution.

Furthermore, the study found that development opportunities, rewards, and organizational support may be more critical factors for lecturers with high self-efficacy. These factors may explain why self-efficacy had an insignificant effect on the talent management of LLDIKTI VI Central Java lecturers. These results differ from previous research by Damanik et al. (2019), which found that self-efficacy plays a crucial role in talent management.

➤ ***Self-Efficacy has a significant effect on lecturers' Achievement Motivation***

The present study investigated the impact of self-efficacy on achievement motivation among lecturers. The findings of the coefficient estimation analysis indicated a significant influence of self-efficacy on achievement motivation. The critical ratio (CR) value of 5.882 was greater than the 1.96 threshold, while the significance value (p-value) of 0.000 was smaller than the 5% significance level. The resulting influence coefficient was 0.301, which was positive. This finding indicates that the higher the lecturer's self-efficacy, the higher their achievement motivation.

The results of this study suggest that lecturers who have high self-confidence in their abilities tend to be more motivated to achieve because they believe that they can successfully overcome the challenges they face. This is consistent with Bandura's theory of self-efficacy, which suggests that self-efficacy influences cognitive aspects related to a person's motivation. Individuals with high self-efficacy are more motivated to carry out a particular task compared to those with low self-efficacy. Moreover, self-efficacy refers to an individual's belief in their ability to succeed in certain tasks. Lecturers with high levels of self-efficacy tend to believe that they can overcome academic challenges, research, or other tasks, which directly influences their motivation to achieve higher levels of success.

Furthermore, the study found that high self-efficacy can strengthen a lecturer's sense of self-esteem and professional identity. By feeling competent in their work, lecturers are more likely to feel satisfied and motivated to achieve higher levels of success, thus validating their abilities and achievements. The findings of this study are consistent with previous research conducted by Damanik et al. (2019), Maraghi et al. (2018), and Silalahi & Silvianita. (2021), which similarly suggest that self-efficacy influences motivation.

➤ ***Self-Efficacy has a significant effect on lecturer Performance***

The coefficient estimate results of the relationship between self-efficacy and lecturer performance display a significant influence, with a CR value of 4.494 and a significance value (p-value) of 0.000. The effect coefficient is 0.240 (positive), indicating that the lecturer's performance improves as their self-efficacy increases. This means that instructors who have high self-confidence in their skills are usually more motivated and capable of completing their academic duties with excellence. Lecturers with high self-efficacy prefer setting ambitious and achievement-oriented objectives, and they believe they have the ability to reach these goals. Consequently, they work harder to accomplish their objectives, leading to more effort and consistency in obtaining peak performance.

➤ ***Transformational Leadership has a significant effect on lecturer Talent Management***

The findings of the current study indicate a significant relationship between transformational leadership and talent management in higher education. The coefficient estimation results reveal a positive and statistically significant influence of transformational leadership on talent management, with a CR value of 5.408 and a significance value of 0.000. These results suggest that leaders with a transformative leadership style, characterized by inspiration, motivation,

and a clear vision, can play a crucial role in identifying, developing, and motivating academic talents in higher education. Furthermore, the results of the hypothesis testing indicate that transformational leadership can help followers to view old problems in new ways, and excite, arouse, and inspire them to exert extra effort in achieving organizational goals. By creating a positive organizational culture that supports talent management, even with limited resources, transformational leaders can help to change followers' awareness of problems and drive them towards achieving organizational goals.

In light of these findings, it is suggested that higher education institutions should prioritize the development of transformational leadership skills among their leaders to enhance talent management practices. This study contributes to the existing literature by highlighting the critical role of transformational leadership in talent management and providing insights into how leaders can promote academic talent development in higher education.

➤ ***Transformational Leadership has a significant effect on lecturers' Achievement Motivation***

The results of the coefficient estimation analysis indicate that transformational leadership has a significant positive influence on achievement motivation. The CR value is 4.656, which is greater than 1.96, and the p-value is 0.000, which is smaller than the 5% significance level. The resulting influence coefficient is 0.260, which means that higher transformational leadership in higher education encourages the lecturers to increase their achievement motivation.

The findings suggest that transformational leadership, which inspires, motivates, and provides a clear vision, can increase lecturers' motivation to achieve higher academic goals. According to Robbins & Judge (2018), a transformational leader stimulates and inspires his followers to do extraordinary things. This leadership style cultivates trust, admiration, loyalty, and respect among followers, which motivates them to exceed their expectations.

One of the main characteristics of transformational leadership is its ability to encourage critical thinking and innovation. Lecturers who feel motivated to innovate, explore new ideas, and contribute to research or education are more likely to achieve higher academic accomplishments. These results align with previous studies conducted by Jiang & Chen (2018) and Suardika (2019).

➤ ***Transformational Leadership has no significant effect on lecturer Performance***

The examination of the relationship between transformational leadership and lecturer performance shows that there is no significant influence of transformational leadership on lecturer performance. The calculated influence coefficient is insignificant, indicating that an increase in transformational leadership does not have a significant impact on improving lecturer performance. This suggests that although transformational leadership is important in creating a positive work environment and motivating staff, its direct effect on lecturer performance is not significant. It is possible that universities with good accreditation face greater challenges in crisis management and recovery, making transformational leadership less effective in addressing day-to-day challenges.

➤ *Talent Management has a significant effect on lecturer Performance*

The analysis of the data reveals that talent management has a significant positive influence on the performance of lecturers in tertiary institutions. The results of the hypothesis testing show that effective talent management policies and strategies can help institutions identify, develop, and make better use of lecturers' academic talents, thereby contributing to improved performance. By offering training, mentoring, and career development opportunities, institutions can enable lecturers to enhance their skills and potential, ultimately improving their teaching, research, and administrative abilities. The obtained influence coefficient of 0.337 indicates that the higher the quality of talent management, the better the performance of lecturers.

➤ *Achievement Motivation has a significant effect on lecturer Performance*

The findings from the coefficient estimation analysis indicate that achievement motivation has a significant influence on lecturer performance. The CR value of 3.964 (greater than 1.96) and a significance value (p-value) of 0.000 (smaller than the 5% significance level) confirm this effect. The resulting influence coefficient is 0.303 (positive), indicating that the higher the lecturer's achievement motivation, the higher their performance.

In addition to the positive impact on performance, achievement motivation also serves as a driving force for lecturers to improve their quality and competence in the academic field. Such motivation results in lecturers feeling satisfied when they achieve new accomplishments, such as obtaining high-quality scientific publications, receiving academic awards, or achieving recognition from their students and peers for their teaching efforts. This drive for self-improvement ultimately encourages lecturers to continue learning and developing their skills, leading to an overall improvement in their performance.

CONCLUSIONS

The results of this research emphasize the significance of lecturer competence in their achievement motivation and performance in higher education. Although lecturer competency does not have a direct impact on talent management at the institution, it has a significant influence on lecturer motivation and performance. Additionally, perceived organizational support plays a crucial role in enhancing talent management and lecturer achievement motivation. Even though it does not affect performance considerably, strong organizational support can facilitate a conducive environment for lecturer development and performance.

On the other hand, transformational leadership significantly influences talent management and lecturers' achievement motivation but does not have an impact on their performance. This highlights the importance of leaders who can inspire and motivate lecturers to achieve greater success, even though improving lecturer performance may not be the top priority in the context of higher education, which faces other challenges. Therefore, talent management and achievement motivation remain essential areas of focus in enhancing the quality and productivity of lecturers in higher education.

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